

ATTITUDES, MOTIVATION, AND ANXIETY ON WRITING ACADEMIC ESSAY AMONG THE SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS OF MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY-SULU

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ABSTRACT

This study is conducted to investigate the attitudes, motivation, and anxiety on writing academic essay among the Senior High School students of Mindanao State University- Sulu, specifically; to determine the level of anxiety when writing academic essay; to investigate the attitude of the students towards writing; to discover the specific factors that contribute to this anxiety as perceived by the students; to find out what motivates the students to write academic essays; and to ascertain if there is a significant difference on the level of essay anxiety among the students when grouped according to strand. The research is quantitative which utilized the descriptive method design to provide the information needed involving 199 students from the STEM and GAS Strand as respondents during the academic year 2023-2024. It utilized stratified random sampling method in selecting the respondents, checklist survey questionnaire in gathering the data, and applied the statistical techniques; Mean and t-test for independent sample to analyze the data. Based on the findings of this research, the Senior High School students of Mindanao State University-Sulu are experiencing moderately-high levels of anxiety towards writing academic essays. It was also found that when the students are segregated based on their academic focus, there is no significant difference on the level of anxiety experienced among the students. Therefore, the researchers suggest to the students, teachers, future researchers, and school administrators that it would be significant to focus on this phenomenon in order to develop a proficient writing capability amongst the students and also for the learners to be able to foster a positive perspective when it comes to writing academic essays.

Keywords: *anxiety, academic essay, essay anxiety, Mindanao State University-Sulu, SHS*

INTRODUCTION

Essay writing is known as an intricate method to assess a student's academic capability in the field of education, as it does not require the student's memorization skills, but instead relies on their cognitive ability for critical reasoning. Since students have to create a piece using the English language, they often find writing to be challenging (Mahmoud, et al., 2020). It is analytical because it needs the writer's understanding of a specific topic and explains it in a cohesive manner, which is why most of the time, an essay is presented from a personal point of view. There are various kinds of academic essays, ranging from argumentative to descriptive, each serving its unique purpose in expressing ideas to be understood by the readers.

Furthermore, easy writing serves as a way of learning for others and learning is an important aspect in education as uttered by Sabbaha et. al., (2024) cited by Abdulmajid et. al., (2024), Mading et. al., (2024), Balla et. al., (2024) and Sakili et. al., (2024) Indeed, learning is the soul of education that eliminates ignorance within an individual's mind, it is an ability influenced by human beings that plays a crucial role in the existence of human life hence, learning is a continuous process and a cognitive task. As a task for cognitive linguistics, writing requires the use of advanced cognitive skills to organize ideas in a way that makes them easier to understand and makes sure that the thoughts being communicated make sense (Jennifer & Ponniah, 2017). The ability of the human mind to construct essays mainly depends on an individual's understanding of a certain topic and the mental process of comprehending the information. Engaging one's cognitive abilities through writing is an excellent tool.

Numerous studies have revealed connections between writing and mental abilities in areas including memory, creativity, critical thinking, language skills, and general wellness. This could act as a catalyst that could trigger the incompetence of the students when trying to write essays. Even though writing essays requires mental faculties, some people may inevitably find the process difficult. This difficulty will then show itself as a phenomenon called Essay Anxiety.

Essay Anxiety, also known as the state of being frightened in terms of writing an essay, concerns the following common problems such as the behavior of the students, stress, or even depression. Few senior high school students at the said institution find it hard to write essays when asked by their teachers as part of a requirement in passing any written work and exams, making them focus most of their time answering the essay questions provided. This is also the reason why most of the time, teachers tend to put more time when the exam reaches the essay category. This exact scenario has become an emergent requisite for some researchers to further investigate the academic essay-writing capabilities of the students to raise awareness and possibly find a plausible understanding of these causes.

Even though many students find writing essays strenuous, some consider this not a problem at all. According to Bulqiyah et al. (2021), another important aspect that has been found to have a major impact on students' writing processes and output is their writing techniques. This means that the strategy implemented by some students when writing affects

the outcome of their writing performance, showing that experience gained from learning background might pose a major difference in why some students perceive writing essays hard while others find it easy. In addition to some senior high school pupils who performed poorly in writing academic essays, understanding the English language should be prioritized and improved to address the poor background of some students when it comes to their English language speaking proficiency.

That is, this paper aims to investigate how writing essays causes anxiety among students, to realize the factors that might contribute to this problem and the factors that could motivate them. The researchers believe that addressing the attitude of the students toward writing academic essays is crucial.

Research that tackles the difficulties of the students in writing academic essays has been accumulating in various settings. However, studies exploring the attitude of the students towards writing academic essays encountered specifically by senior high school students in MSU-Sulu are still very limited. Additionally, there is a scarcity of research on essay anxiety, particularly in terms of examining the variations in anxiety levels among student groups based on academic focus.

Since the setting of this research will be the Senior High School Department of Mindanao State University- Sulu, where the conduct of research employing the exploration of essay anxiety of the students is very few to none, this study will be relevant to explore to find solutions to this problem. Furthermore, the performance of some, if not, then many senior high school students in this setting when writing academic essays is poor. Therefore, this study is timely and applicable to nourish the academic essay writing potential of the students.

Research Questions

This research primarily aimed to delve into the attitude of Senior High School Students at MSU-Sulu toward writing academic essays. Specifically, the researchers were driven to find answers to these particular questions:

- a. What is the level of anxiety experienced by the students when writing academic essays?
- b. What are the attitudes of the students towards writing academic essays?
- c. What are the specific factors contributing to essay anxiety as perceived by the students?
- d. What could motivate the students to write academic essays?
- e. Is there a significant difference in the level of essay anxiety of the student when they are grouped according to their strand?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Mindanao State University- Sulu Senior High School Department, Capitol Site, Jolo, Sulu. Survey questionnaires were given to the selected learners inside their individual classroom or any pleasant spot the selected respondent will decide to go. The location of implementation was selected by the researchers because it is the planned site for the conduct of research, thus, giving the researchers their needed information significant to the exploration. During the second term of the academic year 2023-2024, the study was carried out.

Sampling Method

In this study, the researchers utilized the stratified random sampling method of selecting the respondents of this research. The distribution of the respondents using stratified random sampling is depicted in the table below. The researcher used 4.6% of the population of senior high school students in MSU- Sulu. Out of 1,955, only 90 students are the chosen respondents of this study. Therefore, the STEM has a total sample of 87 and 112 from the GAS strand. Moreover, the respondents of this study were the STEM and GAS strand learners of the aforementioned institution, which has 25 sections and a total student population of 1,955. The researchers will select 51 students from STEM-11, 36 students from STEM-12, 59 students from GAS-11, and 53 students from GAS-12 as respondents of this study. The researchers decided to include the HUMSS strand along with the GAS strand students since the strand is intermixed with the latter and is also a minority within the aforementioned institution.

Research Instrument

The research utilized a checklist questionnaire produced by the researchers to gather the necessary data to answer the research problems. The questionnaire version was developed by the researchers depending on their readings, prior research, relevant published studies, and related literature. SPSS is the same as the statistical app used in the research paper of Sabbaha et. al. (2024) or the so called Statistical Package for Social Sciences was used in calculation and to analyze the data. The requirements for designing efficient data gathering instruments will be subject to consideration when developing the instrument. The researchers also made use of two designs of Likert scale to evaluate the data.

Table 3.2 School recommended scale

Scale	Weighted Mean/ Equivalent	Corresponding Remarks
4	3.26 – 4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.51 – 3.25	Agree
2	1.76 – 2.50	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.75	Strongly Disagree

Table 3.2 Adapted scale on the study of Abu Bakar and Ismail (2020) to assess the level of essay anxiety of the students

Scale	Weighted Mean/ Equivalent	Corresponding Remarks
4	3.25 – 4.00	High
3	2.50 – 3.24	Moderately High
2	1.75 – 2.49	Moderately Low
1	1.00 – 1.74	Low

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following statistical techniques were applied in order to comprehend the data that will be collected from the study subjects: Weighted Mean was used to ascertain the degree of essay anxiety of the students, the attitude of the students towards essay writing, the factors that contribute to the anxiety as perceived by the students, and the factors that could motivate the students into writing academic essays; and t-Test for dependent sample were also employed to determine whether there is a discernible difference between the students' anxiety level regarding essay writing when they are categorized based on their strand.

Scope and Delimitation

This study focuses on the attitudes, motivation, and anxiety of writing academic essays among the Senior High School Students of Mindanao State University-Sulu. The student-respondents of this study is delimited to the 4.6% of the population of senior high school students in MSU- Sulu. Out of 1,955, only 90 students are the chosen respondents of this study. Therefore, the STEM has a total sample of 87 and 112 from the GAS strand. Moreover, the respondents of this study were the STEM and GAS strand learners of the aforementioned institution, which has 25 sections and a total student population of 1,955.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 4.1 The level of Essay Anxiety of the Senior High School Students

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
1. I feel the tension when I write essay.	2.71	.699	Agree
2. I get scared when I encounter essay questions on quizzes and exams.	2.70	.750	Agree
3. Writing essay drains my energy.	2.66	.741	Agree
4. Writing essay makes me nervous.	2.62	.781	Agree
5. Writing essay is scary.	2.57	.794	Agree
6. Negative thoughts enter my mind when I start to write essay.	2.56	.807	Agree

7. My chest feels heavy every time I write essay.	2.55	.708	Agree
8. Writing essay makes me feel unintelligent.	2.44	.813	Disagree
9. Writing essay makes me feel uncomfortable.	2.41	.732	Disagree
10. I easily give up when I write essay.	2.25	.788	Disagree

Grand Mean

2.55

0.76

Moderately High

*Legend: 3.26-4.00 (strongly agree); 2.51-3.25 (agree); 1.76-2.50 (disagree); 1.00-1.75 (strongly disagree).
Level: 3.25-4.00 (High); 2.50-3.24 (Moderately High); 1.75-2.49 (Moderately Low); 1.00-1.74 (Low)*

Table 4.1 presents the Level of essay anxiety of the Senior High School students in Mindanao State University-Sulu. As shown in the table, the grand mean obtained is 2.55 with the verbal description of Moderately High. This signifies that the respondents experience a moderately high level of anxiety towards writing essays.

The respondents agreed to the following statements since it falls between 2.55 to 2.71. The students' chest feels heavy every time they write essay, negative thoughts enter their minds when they start to write essay, writing essay is scary, writing essay makes them nervous, writing essay drains their energy, they get scared when they encounter essay questions on quizzes and exams, and they feel the tension when they write essay. Moreover, the students disagreed with the following statements with a mean of 2.25 to 2.44. They easily give up when they write essays, writing essays makes them feel uncomfortable, and writing essay makes them feel unintelligent. With the of 2.71, the statement "I feel the tension when I write essay" got the highest mean amongst the other statements in the table.

The findings of this research are related to multiple studies such as those of Zhang & Rahimi (2014) that essay anxiety occurs in students when they are asked to write as part of a task to finish, Silveira (2020) discussed that psychological manifestations of anxiety include uneasiness, fear, trembling, and restlessness due to nervous system activity, as defined by Ajmal and Ahmad (2019) and cited by Jailani et. al., (2024), anxiety is a basic human emotion that consists of fear and uncertainty and usually it occurs when individual believes that the event is a threat to self or self-esteem. and the study of Salem & Al Dyiar (2014) which found that learners that get frightened when writing frequently overestimate how tough their writing will be.

Table 4.2 Attitude of Senior High School Students towards Writing Essay.

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
1. Writing essay is important to me as a student.	3.36	.602	Strongly Agree
2. Writing essay improves my skills.	3.26	.577	Strongly Agree

3. Writing essay becomes a space for me to express my thoughts.	3.06	.613	Agree
4. I am used to writing essays.	2.93	.607	Agree
5. I am always prepared when my teacher asks me to write essay.	2.68	.783	Agree
6. I prefer essay compared to other types of exams.	2.67	.778	Agree
7. I have fun when writing essay.	2.67	.752	Agree
8. I know a lot about writing essays.	2.63	.719	Agree
9. Writing essay calms me.	2.61	.693	Agree
10. I consider writing essay as a hobby.	2.53	.716	Agree
Grand Mean	2.84	0.68	Agree

Legend: 3.26-4.00 (strongly agree); 2.51-3.25 (agree); 1.76-2.50 (disagree); 1.00-1.75 (strongly disagree).

Table 4.2 illustrates the attitude of the Senior High School students in Mindanao State University- Sulu towards writing academic essays. As can be seen in the table presented, the grand mean resulted in 2.84, which shows that the students agreed with the statements implemented in the table.

The respondents strongly agreed with the following statements, which has a mean ranging from 3.26 to 3.36. The students strongly admit that writing essay improves their skills and is important to them as a student. Furthermore, the students agreed that writing essay is a hobby, writing essay calms them, they know a lot about writing essay, they have fun writing essay, they prefer essay compared to other types of exams, they are always prepared when their teachers ask them to write essay, and that they consider essay writing as a space for them to express their feelings with a mean ranging from 2.53 to 3.06.

The findings in this table are significantly related to the study of Jabali (2018), where in his study, he found out that learners have a positive attitude towards writing.

Table 4.3 Factors that contribute to the Essay Anxiety of the students

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
1. I get essay anxiety when I don't understand the question being asked.	2.92	.781	Agree
2. I get essay anxiety when my teacher asks me to write long essays.	2.80	.725	Agree

3. I get essay anxiety because I have weak vocabulary of words.	2.78	.712	Agree
4. Tiredness in the classroom gives me essay anxiety.	2.77	.664	Agree
5. I get essay anxiety because I am weak when it comes to English grammar.	2.75	.714	Agree
6. I get essay anxiety because I don't have enough study.	2.73	.757	Agree
7. I get essay anxiety because I am not good in using the English language.	2.73	.750	Agree
8. I get essay anxiety because I don't have enough confidence to write essays.	2.71	.663	Agree
9. I get essay anxiety because I don't know how to construct sentences.	2.67	.703	Agree
10. I get essay anxiety because our classroom is hot.	2.67	.853	Agree
11. I get essay anxiety during exams because I am used to using the internet when writing essay on assignments.	2.57	.781	Agree
12. I get essay anxiety because I am not used to writing essays.	2.55	.756	Agree
13. I get essay anxiety because there are too many students in our classroom and I feel uncomfortable.	2.54	.808	Agree
14. I get essay anxiety because my teacher is very strict.	2.50	.710	Disagree
15. I get essay anxiety because I don't know how to write an essay.	2.46	.777	Disagree
Grand Mean	2.68	0.74	Agree

Legend: 3.26-4.00 (strongly agree); 2.51-3.25 (agree); 1.76-2.50 (disagree); 1.00-1.75 (strongly disagree).

Table 4.3 illustrates the factors that contribute to the essay anxiety of the students in Mindanao State University-Sulu towards writing academic essay. With an overall mean of 2.68, the findings implied that the respondents agreed with the factors cited that contribute to their essay anxiety.

The respondents agreed on the following factors since it falls between 2.54 to 2.92. These factors that contribute to their essay anxiety include being uncomfortable because of too many students inside the classroom, not being used to writing essays, depending too much on the internet, inability to construct sentences, the temperature inside their classroom, the lack of confidence to write, lack of study regarding the essay topic, inefficiency in using the English language, weakness when it comes to English grammar, tiredness inside the

classroom, weakness in vocabulary of words, the required length of essay to be written, and because they don't understand the question or topic of the essay. At the same time, the students disagreed with the following factors with a mean of 2.46 to 2.50. They get essay anxiety because they don't know how to write an essay and because their teacher is very strict. Furthermore, the statement "I get essay anxiety when I don't understand the question being asked" is the most favored factor with a mean of 2.92 and the verbal description of "Agree".

These findings are related to the study of Pongsapan (2022), whose study showed the factors that contribute to a learner's essay anxiety include communication apprehension, test anxiety, and fear of negative evaluation, and Jawas (2019), which discovered that students' writing anxiety is significantly influenced by them in-class essays, which means that the environment the learners are present in has huge consequences on the anxiousness felt by the students. This problem is the result of any factors by the environment that they are in when constructing academic requirements such as essay writing.

Table 4.4 Students' Motivation for Writing Essays

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
1. I am motivated to write essays because I want to improve my writing skills.	3.36	.650	Strongly Agree
2. I get motivated to write essays when I understand the essay question very well.	3.31	.622	Strongly Agree
3. I am motivated to write essays when our teachers do not judge what we wrote.	3.30	.687	Strongly Agree
4. I get motivated to write essay when the teacher does not limit the length of the essay that we will write.	3.27	.564	Strongly Agree
5. I am motivated to write essays because writing lets me express my thoughts.	3.19	.654	Agree
6. I like writing essays because it does not require me to memorize anything.	3.18	.665	Agree
7. I am motivated to write essays because it helps me express my feelings.	3.17	.657	Agree
8. I am motivated to write essays because I am eager to learn.	3.16	.647	Agree
9. I am motivated to write essays because I love writing.	2.98	.647	Agree
10. I like writing essays because I am good at writing.	2.75	.721	Agree

Grand Mean **3.17** **0.65** **Agree**

Legend: 3.26-4.00 (strongly agree); 2.51-3.25 (agree); 1.76-2.50 (disagree); 1.00-1.75 (strongly disagree).

Table 4.4 presents the Motivation of the Senior High School students of Mindanao State University-Sulu into writing essays. As shown in the table, the grand mean obtained 3.17 with the verbal description of Agree. This implies that the respondents agreed to the statements that motivated them to write essay.

The students specifically showed strong agreement to the statements that motivate them to write essay which includes being motivated when there is no minimum or maximum limit to the words that they can write when constructing essay, when the teachers do not judge their essay output, when they have clear understanding of the essay questions, and because they want to improve their writing skills which ranged from the mean of 3.27 to 3.36. Moreover, with a mean ranging from 2.75 to 3.19, the students agreed that they get motivated to write essay because they are good at writing, they love to write, they are eager to learn because writing essay helps them express their feelings, it does not require them to memorize anything, and it lets them show their thoughts. The statement “I am motivated to write essays because I want to improve my writing skills” resulted in the highest mean amongst other statements with the description of Agree.

The findings in this table show a connection with the study of (Arfiana et al., 2022). She found out that there is a significant connection between the learners’ writing proficiency and motivation. When writing, students tend to do better when they feel encouraged with support from various factors which results as an advantage when writing essays. It is arguable that the primary factor contributing to pupils’ excellent writing is their motivation (Arfiana et al., 2022).

Table 4.5 Difference in the Essay Anxiety between STEM and GAS strand students

Variable	STEM		GAS		t(8)	p-value
	M	SD	M	SD		
Strand	2.5	.52820	2.6	.52895	-1.760	0.080

P-value of 0.05 and below= null hypothesis rejected; P-value above 0.05= null hypothesis accepted

Table 4.5 shows if there is a difference in essay anxiety experienced by the Senior High School students of Mindanao State University-Sulu when they are grouped according to their strand.

The findings showed that there is no significant difference on the essay anxiety experienced between the STEM strand (Mean= 2.5) and GAS strand (Mean= 2.6) students, proven with the p-value of .080 which signifies that the null hypothesis is to be accepted.

The study that can be aligned with the results in this table is the study of Desamparado et al. (2019) where accordingly, there is no discernible connection between stress levels and a students’ material, skills/performance, or attitude when they are grouped by strand.

Conclusions

The study has been conducted, and the results revealed that the findings imply a significant effect for the benefit of the students. The results showed that the learners experience a moderately high level of essay anxiety, and an overall positive attitude towards it. It also showed the various factors that contribute to this phenomenon and the factors that motivate them to write. Moreover, it can be seen in the results that there is no significant difference in the essay anxiety experienced by the students when they are grouped according to strand.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were based from the previous chapter of the study;

- A. For the students, enhancing their essay writing capability will reduce the essay anxiety that they perceive to be true by invoking a more lucid understanding of it. This can be done by practicing the basics of writing, enhancing their vocabulary and grammar through reading, and asking their teachers or writing experts for clarifications when there is something that they do not understand regarding writing essays.
- B. For the teachers, it is important to practice consideration and guide the students when they find it hard to construct essays. Realizing that their educational attainment is different compared to the students would also be helpful for them to understand that some students will not be able to follow if they raise the standards too much, therefore giving essay writing a bad reputation to the students.
- C. For the school administrators, providing a curriculum that is easy for the students to understand and follow will be convenient in order to reduce the anxiety that they feel every time they are asked to write by their teachers.
- D. For the future researchers, may the problems and findings of this study serve as a guide for them to widen their perspective on essay anxiety and how it significantly affects the student's confidence in the field of writing.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The participants of the conducted research were notified that the information collected will be exploited to find answers to the problems of research and make recommendations for the improvement of writing skills of the senior high school students in MSU-Sulu. This statement will be made public in the conduct of the survey. The participants of the respondents were those who were elaborated in the research participants. Additionally, the respondents were informed that recommendations will be provided at the conclusion and will be free to express their opinions about what should and should not be done. In order to

comply with all confidentiality laws, the identities of the respondents were not disclosed anywhere. Furthermore, a significant percentage of the suggestions originated from the researchers.

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